

Saudi women's smartphones

A double-edged sword

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The smartphone has significantly contributed to empowering Saudi women. However, it functions as a driver of empowerment primarily within a neoliberal feminist framework, while also serving as a powerful tool of control in an ultra-conservative society.

In January 2019, the world was captivated by the case of Rahaf Mohammed al-Qunun, a Saudi woman who fled her family and became stranded in Thailand after her passport was confiscated. Armed with her smartphone, she turned to social media to alert international organizations to her potentially grim fate; a story that, incidentally, reinforced the stereotypical Western portrayal of Saudi women as subordinate to patriarchy and Islam.

The reaction of the Saudi *charg d'affaires* on Twitter (X) – suggesting that the authorities should have confiscated Rahaf's phone – illustrates the power this object has acquired. Without attributing to it autonomous agency, we can nevertheless consider the smartphone a catalyst for certain societal transformations, particularly with regard to Saudi women.

Yet the smartphone remains a double-edged sword. As a tool of emancipation, it has reshaped women's relationship to public space, challenged gender segregation, expanded social interactions, awakened feminist consciousness, and loosened the grip of certain normative constraints. But as an instrument of political and social control, it is also used to surveil dissident voices and scrutinize women's behaviour in the name of preserving Saudi traditions.

In a society marked by the paradoxical coexistence of ultra-rigorism and modernism, the smartphone has not determined – but rather amplified – the transformations underway,

particularly as female empowerment has become a strategic lever for economic growth and for projecting a progressive national image. In tracing how the smartphone has contributed to subverting certain norms, we focus here on the chiaroscuro uses it has fostered in relation to mobility, subjectivity, and activism.

The subversion of norms by the smartphone

In the 2000s, the introduction of the smartphone in Saudi Arabia sparked controversy because of the threats it posed to the authoritarian regime. With its functionalities, it could undermine the protection of girls, the control of ideas, and religious and cultural values, as well as challenge the patriarchal structure that maintains the gender order.

Despite the initial ban on smartphones with cameras, the authorities soon had to confront the explosive growth of connectivity, fuelled by the rise of early smartphones such as the Blackberry in 2003 [1]. Popular among users but troubling for the authorities because of its encrypted communications, the Blackberry was followed by the iPhone 2G, equipped with a camera. Despite restrictions on certain applications (like FaceTime), it marked a significant change: photography became subversive. Taking pictures of humans was considered a corrupting threat.

The introduction of smartphones raised concerns: those equipped with cameras were illegal, and their use was condemned by religious authorities, who denounced them as invasive of privacy, even “obscene” [2], and dangerous for women. Nonetheless, photographs circulated—not without consequences. Girls were expelled from university for taking pictures of unveiled classmates, fines were imposed, and fights broke out over compromising images [3].

Charged with enforcing public morality, the religious police (the muttawas) cracked down. But the ban could not withstand social reality. A conflict arose between religious authorities and manufacturers, who cited the technical impossibility of blocking cameras or producing a Saudi-specific model. The Kingdom eventually backtracked [4], to the satisfaction of Saudi youth seeking openness.

Fuelled by the spread of smartphones (mobile penetration was 12% in 2001, compared with 170% in 2013 [5]), connectivity increased rapidly. As part of this digital transition, Saudi women quickly adopted digital tools to access the public sphere [6]. Confined to

the home due to limited access to the labour market and restrictions on movement, urban Saudi women were, contrary to the Western trend, initially more connected than men [7].

Today, in this ultra-conservative state – one of the most connected in the world [8] – these fears have largely dissipated. Social media and photography are now widely accepted by urban families, particularly the most privileged. The power of the religious police has diminished, and selfies or family photographs have become common practice in urban environments [9]. From initial fears to widespread acceptance, the smartphone has extended subversive practices across broader populations and territories.

Smartphone agentivity and mobility

In the 2000s, the advent of the connected mobile phone [10] freed Saudi women from the spatial constraints that had confined them to the private sphere. Subject to the guardianship system – which required authorization to travel and imposed burdensome administrative formalities – women were restricted in their movements and faced obstacles in accessing the labour market [11].

As part of government digitisation initiatives, the Interior Ministry created several applications, including Absher in 2015, to facilitate administrative procedures such as exit permits for Saudi women. Although perceived in the West as a surveillance tool that controls women [12], the app has been more positively received in Saudi Arabia because it offers flexibility. Thanks to digital infrastructure, guardians no longer had to travel to offices, which is especially advantageous in congested Riyadh. Moreover, the app could be circumvented if women had access to their guardian's codes, allowing them to obtain exit permits themselves [13].

Thus, while perpetuating power structures such as guardianship, the smartphone also enabled women to circumvent them. It is both a tool for monitoring girls and one that frees them from domestic confinement by allowing mobility in public spaces. Celebrated as a "mobility belt," the smartphone facilitates geolocation in densely populated cities and provides reassurance for night-time outings. For women long banned from driving, transport apps such as Uber or Careem [14] made the smartphone a substitute for drivers or family members.

Smartphone agentivity and subjectivation

In a society marked by gender segregation [15] and strict dress codes, such as the widespread *abāya* (often black in Riyadh) until 2019, or even the *niqāb* in traditional neighbourhoods, Saudi women were long invisibilised in public space. They were marginalised, particularly after the oil boom, which pushed the state to adopt a more conservative stance and discipline bodies [16]. Against this oppressive backdrop—but also in the context of progressive reforms aimed at women—the smartphone became a companion on the road, a “technology of the self” [17], a “cognitive prosthesis,” or even a “mirror of the self” [18].

It has allowed Saudi women to reclaim their sense of self and build identities long repressed by the social order. In a society where collective values dominate and intimacy is understood differently than in the West [19], the connected mobile has become both the object and territory for exploring intimacy, a space for confidences and hidden revelations. It enables discreet communication (e.g., messaging systems) in large households, allows anonymous storytelling via pseudonyms or anonymous platforms, and facilitates sharing intimate information in a society often labelled gossipy [20], where psychological services [21] remain taboo.

The smartphone thus becomes a means of self-exposure within reputational limits, allowing fragments of selfhood to be shared despite collective constraints. In Saudi Arabia, privacy is not limited to the individual but encompasses the family to preserve honour [22]. By promoting values of an “autonomous self” [23], social networks have reshaped conceptions of private life in the Kingdom.

For Saudi women, previously invisible, these platforms have provided a way to assert themselves, gain recognition, and claim a place in a society that long excluded them, often for political rather than religious reasons [24]. Visual platforms such as Snapchat, Instagram, and TikTok enable them to represent themselves beyond the homogenisation imposed by the *abāya*. Through filters and ephemeral “snaps” [25], Saudi women have outwitted social and Islamic norms [26][27] to expose themselves differently.

Mastering privacy settings has encouraged strategies to align with cultural codes—or sometimes to transgress them. Applications with filters are used to reveal femininity, perform makeup culture, or even cross-dress.

The smartphone itself, as part of body postures and performances, contributes to subjectivity. It is used to style the self [28], as a “show-off” accessory to demonstrate distinction, even under a niqāb. It functions as a screen object to escape the male gaze in the street, a transitional object [29], cherished to the point of being granted near-subject status.

Smartphone agentivity and activism

The smartphone has also been central to both liberal and conservative “feminist” mobilisations. While the former fight for rights perceived in the West as fundamental – such as the right to drive or to exercise guardianship – the latter demand greater justice between men and women in accordance with Islam [30]. From a Western lens, the most emblematic campaigns concern the right to drive [31] or to escape male guardianship, campaigns revitalised in the digital age [32] and fuelled by the Arab Spring. Activists launched the Women2Drive campaign in December 2010 to encourage women to drive.

Saudi activist Manal al-Sharif became a leading figure when she posted a video of herself driving in May 2011 [33]. Her arrest drew national and international attention to the Women2Drive movement, in which around forty women drove in defiance of the ban, filming and tweeting their acts. The movement spread through hashtags like #Women2Drive.

Two years later, the campaign of 26 October 2013 was organised via social media under #Oct26driving. Repression was severe, with activists pressured and intimidated by their families to stop. To everyone’s surprise, women were finally allowed to drive as of 24 June 2018.

Another major campaign targeted male guardianship [34], which long reduced Saudi women to minors for life. In 2016, following a Human Rights Watch report [35], Saudi women launched a campaign challenging the requirement to obtain guardian consent for work, travel, or marriage. Supported by Western voices, hashtags like #TogetherToEndMaleGuardianship [36], #IamMyOwnGuardian [37], and #StopEnslavingSaudiWomen [38] spread widely.

The campaign mobilised Saudi women of different generations who had never before engaged politically [39]. But support was not unanimous. For many conservatives,

guardianship protected women, and counter-hashtags like #GuardianshipIsForHerNotAgainstHer circulated widely.

Such demands diverge from Western feminist norms and highlight tensions between Western and Arab perspectives. They expose the risk of speaking “for” so-called subalterns, reducing feminism to a secular or liberal framework.

In 2019, Mohammed bin Salman’s decree removing the requirement for women to obtain guardian permission for travel marked the end of these campaigns, though guardianship still applies in marriage and childcare [41].

Smartphone empowerment: a sham?

Although the smartphone has supported emancipatory practices, the meaning and scope of this emancipation deserve scrutiny. From a neoliberal perspective, the smartphone appears as a driver of women’s empowerment, in line with Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030, which promotes economic participation for women. Platforms like Instagram [42] facilitated urban women’s entrepreneurship, providing flexibility to balance professional and domestic responsibilities [43].

In reality, in today’s digital economy [44], Saudi women’s empowerment largely reflects neoliberal feminism, which values individual initiative and entrepreneurship [45] at the expense of collective or political struggle. Meanwhile, the smartphone remains a powerful tool for surveillance—by both authorities and peers. The autocratic regime uses it to monitor, intimidate, and repress in the name of national security.

Thus, while the smartphone has helped women gain autonomy, it has also worked against them. A tool of freedom can simultaneously reduce that freedom to nothing. Twitter, for example, saved activists like Manal al-Sharif [46] but also became a site of propaganda and harassment linked to the regime [47].

Through troll farms [48], propaganda campaigns [49], or spyware such as Pegasus, dissidents are monitored with disastrous consequences [50]. Digital repression disproportionately affects women [51], who, due to honour culture, face stricter surveillance, risk forced returns, and suffer transnational repression [52]. Measures under MBS that appear to favour women have not lifted restrictions online [53].

Despite the 2018 law against sexual harassment, women who reported abuse online faced arrest and intimidation [54]. Peer control, encouraged by the state through apps like Kollona Amn, further amplifies surveillance. While some women appreciate such tools, it is often women who suffer the brunt of this control.

In conservative society, a woman's "moral fault" tarnishes her family's reputation, while a man's transgression affects only himself [55]. Women are therefore forced to discipline their visibility online, as deviation may lead to public shaming or even honour killings [56].

Empowerment is thus chiaroscuro. From an individualistic, state-promoted vision, Saudi women appear more autonomous. The same applies if we consider subversive acts against religious and conservative norms. The smartphone has undeniably amplified change, enabling women to coordinate, publicise, and perform feminist mobilisations. Its technical and aesthetic affordances have enhanced subjectivity, opened new spaces, and facilitated professional integration compatible with gender roles.

Yet this conception reflects a liberal framework that equates subversion with individual resistance. A collective and political approach [57] produces a more nuanced picture. Empowerment and self-determination remain conditioned by state and peer surveillance, especially for women from conservative or rural families [58]. In feminist theory, empowerment has often implied transformation of the oppressed.

From a Western perspective, conservative women appear submissive, trapped in patriarchal ideology [59]. But the desire to resist domination is neither universal nor natural. One can conform to Islamic norms and still find fulfilment.

It is therefore inconsistent – and ignorant – to suggest that smartphones empower only those Saudi women who campaign for Western-style rights, while denying empowerment to those who act within Islamic frameworks [60][61]. Such a view reduces empowerment to secular liberal feminism and erases agency within religion.

Indeed, if the smartphone has enabled all women to act, we must ask whether the digital empowerment of some has come at the expense of others. For conservative women, empowerment can mean maintaining segregation as a way to protect women's rights [62]. It is therefore legitimate to question whether digital permeability undermines the struggles and aspirations of the most conservative, for whom religion itself is a lever of emancipation [63].

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